

Learning from Long-Term Care practices
for the European Care Strategy

REASONED BIBLIOGRAPHY

Deliverable no. D2.1

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Executive summary

As part of the LeTs-Care analysis of the diverse challenges in long-term care (LTC) systems across the seven European countries under study – Austria, Denmark, Italy, Lithuania, Portugal, Spain and The Netherlands – the research team conducted a review of the (grey and scientific) national literature. The present deliverable provides information on the resulting bibliographical database that is made available open access by means of a spreadsheet.

The database will be updated throughout the project's life span.

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1. Aims and scope

1.1 *Reasoned bibliography within LeTs-Care WP2*

Within the LeTs-Care project, WP2 aims to provide a new, in-depth, reflexive understanding of LTC challenges across national and local contexts for and with stakeholders and policy makers (Research Objective 1; Pillar 1 of Methodology).

The focus is on the diverse challenges in long-term care (LTC) systems across the seven European countries under study – Austria, Denmark, Italy, Lithuania, Portugal, Spain and The Netherlands – in relation to national and local contexts, varying degrees of decentralization, and socio-economic inequalities. The research also seeks to clarify the different meanings of common and taken-for-granted LTC terms and concepts used by stakeholders and policymakers.

Among the research activities embedded in WP2 is the collection and systematization of relevant national and international literature, which feeds into the analysis of the contextualized challenges.

The literature review was aimed at collecting existing scientific and grey literature about current challenges and strategies in long-term care. More specifically, the aim of the bibliography was also to collect analysis on the meanings of key concepts - “need”, “care”, “quality of care” “quality of care work”, “sustainability”, “inequalities” – in order to contribute at the achievement of the project’s objectives and to provide a new, in-depth, reflexive understanding of LTC challenges across national and local contexts.

Given the LeTs-Care open science approach, the literature review feeds into a reasoned bibliographical database that is made available both to the research community and to the public.

The database containing the reviewed literature items is open to integration throughout the duration of the LeTs-Care project, based on the further research endeavors of the Consortium and on input from other researchers, stakeholders and policymakers.

The final version of the database will be published at the end of the project.

1.2 *Aims and scope of the Deliverable*

The present deliverable illustrates the methods of the literature review and presents the bibliographical database.

In particular it contains illustrations of:

- the criteria and procedure for the literature review;
- the features of the bibliographic database;
- the accessibility to the data.

The database itself is attached to this deliverable.

2. Methods of the literature review

The aim of the review was to answer the research questions of the project with reference to the seven countries under study. The methods have been adapted to this goal and to the characteristics of the literature to be reviewed. In particular, given the fact that the national scientific literature is not necessarily indexed by bibliographic electronic databases, the research team needed to develop a flexible search strategy. In what follows we illustrate the choices that have been made and the features of the produced bibliographical dataset.

2.1 Documents' types and contents

The review encompasses journal articles, working papers, book chapters, books, research reports that focus on debates, policy description and analysis of care-related practices in the field of long-term care, critical perspectives, etc.

2.2 Time coverage

The review covers a 10-year period (2014-2024). In addition, particularly relevant documents dating before 2014 have been added to the selection.

2.3 Geographical coverage

The review covers the literature relevant to the LeTs-Care study in the seven project countries: Austria, Denmark, Italy, Lithuania, The Netherlands, Portugal, Spain.

In addition, relevant international literature which focusses on more than one country, including one of the countries under study, has been added.

2.4 Search methods and instruments

The search was conducted through a combination of different methods and instruments, to enhance coverage of relevant and pertinent bibliographical items:

- International bibliographical electronic databases (e.g. Scopus, WOS, Google Scholar)
- national-based electronic databases
- websites of research projects and of national (and regional) relevant institutions/ organisations
- the reference list of the identified items
- the suggestions of the Associate partners and other stakeholders involved in the research operation (e.g. interviews) and in dissemination events (other mapped stakeholders).

2.5 Search criteria

In the search through electronic bibliographical databases and on the internet, queries were based on strings that matched both the long-term care domain and one or more of the topics under investigation. In both cases, the English terms used in the international debate and literature needed to be adapted to the specificities of the national contexts and the way in which they are designated in the national contexts and in the national languages. Table 1 provides an overview of the English terms that have guided the search for both the domain and the topics.

DOMAIN		TOPICS	
INVESTIGATED DOMAIN	ENGLISH TERMS GUIDING SEARCH	INVESTIGATED TOPIC	ENGLISH TERMS GUIDING SEARCH
Long-term care	Long-term care Older people's care Care for disabled people	Need	Care needs, need forecasting Care demand Chronic illness, morbidity Need assessment Chronic illness Activities of daily living Dementia Disability Autonomy/dependency
		Care and quality of care	Home care Residential care Nursing homes Cash for care Coverage rates of in-kind services/cash benefits Intensity of in-kind/cash benefits Quality of care
		Care work and Quality of care work	Care work Care workers Care professionals Care assistants Care shortages Migrant care workers Informal care Family care Volunteering
		Inequality	Gender gap/inequalities Socio-economic inequalities Territorial/regional inequalities
		Sustainability	Financial sustainability LTC costs Cost projections/forecasting Social sustainability Environmental sustainability

Table 1 – Domain and Topic definition for literature search

2.6 Inclusion and exclusion

All items identified through the interrogation of bibliographical databases, as well as those identified through other channels (see above) have been assessed against the above illustrated criteria. Only the items that were relevant to the LeTs-Care research questions, and in particular the identification

of the “meanings” and of the challenges analysed by the project were retained, based on a reading of the title, abstract and, in case of doubt, of the full text.

3. Reasoned bibliography database

The technical infrastructure of the database is an Excel spreadsheet. The bibliographical database contains a table with 23 columns with the information presented in Table 2.

STRUCTURE OF THE BIBLIOGRAPHICAL DATABASE	
Type	Book/Book Chapter/Journal/Article/In Proceedings/Thesis/Report
Author/s	Name(s) Surname(s), Name(s) Surname(s), ... and Name(s) Surname(s),
Year	yyyy
Title	Title of the article/book chapter/working paper/report
LeTs-Care Country	Austria/Denmark/Italy/Lithuania/the Netherlands/Portugal/Spain/International
Comparative	YES/NO
Needs	YES/blank
Care and Quality of Care	YES/ blank
Care work and Quality of care work	YES/ blank
Sustainability	YES/ blank
Inequalities	YES/ blank
Journal	Name of the journal (for journal articles)
Issue	Issue no.
Volume	Volume no.
Pages	XX-XX
DOI	DOI no.
Editor	Name of editor
Book Title	Title of the book that includes the chapter
ISBN	xxxx-xxxx
ISSN	xxxx-xxxx
Publisher	Name of the Publisher
City	Name of the publishing City
Url	https://

Table 2: Reasoned bibliography database

Columns: “Type”, “Author/s”, “Year”, “Title”, “Journal”, “Issue”, “Volume”, “Pages”, “DOI”, “Editor”, “Book title”, “ISBN”, “ISSN”, “Publisher” and “City” provide bibliographical information about each item.

The column “LeTs-Care Country” indicates which of the seven countries under study the item focusses on (possibly alongside other countries not included in the project). Items focusing on

other/multiple countries are marked as “international”. The column “Comparative” indicates if the item has a comparative perspective.

The columns “Needs”, “Care and quality of care”, “Care work and quality of care work”, “Sustainability”, “Inequalities” indicate if the item has *specific* interests for the five “meanings” studied within the project. When this is the case, “Yes” appears in the column. These columns can be filtered to cluster literature according to research interests. An empty field does not necessarily exclude that the item contains related elements. Therefore, these filters should be used in a flexible way alongside other search methods (title, country, etc.).

Column “URL” provides the link to the document (when available).

3.1 Accessibility of the database

In the framework of open science, the bibliographical database is publicly accessible and downloadable.

The database does not contain the full texts of the reviewed documents. When available, they can easily be found thanks to the DOI and/or URL contained in the database.